

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN BANKING SYSTEM

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Annotation: The increasing adoption of digital technologies in the banking industry has led to significant changes in the way banks operate, interact with customers, and process payments, while also presenting challenges related to cybersecurity, data privacy, and the need for ongoing innovation.

Key words: Digital technologies, online banking, apps, cyber attacks, data, payment methods, digitalization of economy, innovations, digital economy.

The banking industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, with the increasing adoption of digital technologies having a transformative impact on the sector. Digital technologies have allowed banks to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance the customer experience. However, this digital transformation has also presented new challenges, such as the need to address cybersecurity threats, ensure data privacy, and keep up with ongoing innovation.

Graph №1 «Digital banking users and penetration»¹

Digital technologies have had a transformative impact on nearly every aspect of modern society, including the banking industry. Over the past few decades, banks have invested heavily in digital technologies, in an effort to make banking more convenient, secure and accessible to customers. This article will explore some of the key ways in which digital technologies are changing the banking industry, and the challenges and opportunities that arise as a result.

One of the most significant ways in which digital technologies are transforming banking is through online banking and mobile banking apps. These technologies allow customers to check their balances, transfer funds, pay bills, and apply for loans, all from the comfort of their own homes or on-the-go. This has made banking much more convenient for customers, and has helped to reduce wait times at physical bank branches. At the same time, banks have had to invest in sophisticated cybersecurity measures to protect customer data from cyber attacks and fraud.

Another area where digital technologies are having a major impact on banking is in the realm of payment processing. The rise of digital payment methods, such as e-wallets, mobile payments, and contactless payments, has meant that banks must adapt to new payment processing technologies and systems. This has led to the development of faster payment systems, such as instant payments, which allow for real-time transfer of funds between accounts. These faster payment systems are particularly useful for businesses, which rely on quick and efficient payment processing to keep their operations running smoothly.

Digital technologies are also transforming the way banks interact with their customers. Customer service is increasingly being handled through digital channels, such as chatbots and virtual assistants, which can help to answer customer queries and resolve issues in real-time. This has helped to improve customer satisfaction, as customers can get the help they need quickly and easily, without having to wait on hold or visit a physical branch.

However, with the many benefits that digital technologies offer to the banking industry, there are also some challenges and risks that must be addressed. Cybersecurity is one major challenge, as banks must ensure that their systems and data are secure from cyber attacks and data breaches. Additionally, the rise of digital technologies has also led to concerns about data privacy, as banks must

<https://www.insiderintelligence.com/insights/digital-banking-trends/>

be transparent about how they collect and use customer data, and ensure that customer data is protected from unauthorized access or use.

Here are some of the most commonly used digital tools and techniques in the banking sector.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

Digital assistants and chatbots leverage AI-based banking tools to provide customers with the information they need to solve various problems. AI is also useful for analyzing and managing data, securing it, and improving the customer experience. For example, AI-based analytics can process consumer data in seconds to detect recurring patterns.

Machine learning is a related concept, allowing banks to collect, store, and compare customer data in real time. One of the main benefits of using ML for banking is fraud detection. Machine learning solutions can easily detect changes in user behavior and take rapid, preventative action.

Cloud Computing and Banking APIs

Cloud computing is the most popular technology in banking and finance. Cloud-based services improve operations, increase productivity, and deliver products and services instantly. Integrating with the cloud also allows banks to use banking APIs. These APIs facilitate data sharing and improve the overall customer experience.

Big Data Analytics²

Customers today don't view the banking sector as they did ten years ago. Big data-based technologies are helping banks analyze customer spending patterns, monitor risks associated with specific persons or entities, manage feedback, and build loyalty.

Many banks can leverage the insights from big data to satisfy and retain customers. Data analytics solutions offer new opportunities for the banking industry, allowing financial institutions to respond quickly to evolving market demands.

Blockchain³

Any discussion of digital transformation in the banking sector would be incomplete without mentioning blockchain. Financial institutions integrate blockchain to increase the security of data transactions, improve accuracy, and enhance user interfaces.

<https://www.tableau.com/learn/articles/big-data-analytics#:~:text=Big%20data%20analytics%20describes%20the,the%20help%20of%20newer%20tools.>
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/blockchain.asp>

Today, many customers trust blockchain solutions that make transactions and other banking more convenient and transparent. The merging of blockchain and the Internet of Things (BIoT) is one of the main trends in digital banking technology.

Reinventing Consumer Experience

Banking providers aim to make their consumer experience as frictionless as possible, meeting customers' minimum expectations of ease and convenience. Providers must identify the most important aspects of the consumer journey based on varying consumer expectations. Ultimately, they aim to digitize the entire process to meet consumer experience demands and free up employees for higher-value tasks.

Finding the parts of the consumer journey with the greatest impact requires research. Businesses should go over their customer transaction history to identify problem areas. Each improved, digitized customer experience component significantly impacts the overall business.

Leveraging Data Analytics

Credit unions and banks can use data to improve their understanding of consumers, identify opportunities, and cut costs. Financial institutions can use advanced data analytics to predict loan defaults or identify underpaying customers.

For example, granular cluster analytics helps compare individual products to the average product mix for a given consumer type. This information facilitates cross-selling and customer relationship management.

Organizations can mine data to better target customers and prioritize business leads. Data mining also helps improve pricing options—identifying customers who might be paying for services they don't need or who receive payable services for free. Businesses can also perform behavioral analysis to determine customer loyalty and improve retention.

Building a New Operating Model

Consumers demand a fast, convenient digital experience, and human support for complex services and technical issues. Banking providers must find the right balance between digitization and human experience.

There are three ways to operate a digital business:

- **Business-as-usual digital model**—the management team continues to operate, focusing on small, incremental digitization efforts. This model is cost-effective and low risk, but is less suited to businesses that rely

heavily on legacy systems. It is best suited for providers in the early stages of transformation.

- **New business model**—the banking provider establishes a new business team that includes someone in charge of digital processes. This model significantly improves customer experience and offers greater accountability than the business-as-usual model. However, it is more complicated to manage given the creation of a new digital business department, especially where legacy systems are in use. It is best suited for the middle-to-advanced stages of transformation.
- **Digital native model**—the company implements a new digital bank with a dedicated technology stack. This model focuses on customer recruitment and enables fast, deep impacts without legacy systems slowing down the digital transformation process. However, it can be challenging to persuade existing customers to switch to the new bank. This strategy is best suited for highly advanced digital transformation stages.

These operating models are not mutually exclusive organizations often use different models for different business lines and markets.

Digital Transformation in Banking with Cloud Volumes ONTAP⁴

Cloud computing is at the core of digital transformation, elevating it from the adoption stage of digital technology to include also the tools, rebuilding process, and the experience of a virtual environment that is accessible from anywhere. In order for an organization to achieve its goals and secure future viability, it needs to adopt a cloud-first or hybrid cloud management strategy.

NetApp Cloud Volumes ONTAP, the leading enterprise-grade storage management solution, delivers secure, proven storage management services on AWS, Azure and Google Cloud. Cloud Volumes ONTAP capacity can scale into the petabytes, and it supports various use cases such as file services, databases, DevOps or any other enterprise workload, with a strong set of features including high availability, data protection, storage efficiencies, Kubernetes integration, and more.

NetApp and Cloud Volumes ONTAP play a key role in the cloud transformation process, helping enterprises move workloads and data to the cloud securely, manage them efficiently, and integrate them with modern cloud technologies. This frees the organizations from the burden of managing large-scale storage infrastructure, and allows them to focus on their core business. In particular,

<https://www.netapp.com/data-management/ontap-data-management-software/>

Cloud Volumes ONTAP assists with cloud migration in digital transformation projects. Learn more about how Cloud Volumes ONTAP helps with lift and shift cloud migration.

In conclusion, digital technologies are transforming the banking industry in many ways, from online and mobile banking to faster payment processing and improved customer service. While there are challenges and risks associated with these technologies, the benefits of digital technologies are clear, and banks will need to continue to adapt and evolve in order to stay competitive in the rapidly-changing digital landscape

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